

Crisis Management of Maritime Accidents in the European Union: An Analytical Approach

Nazzar Niyaz Ahmed Al Zadjali¹, Seyed Behbood Issa Zadeh² Claudia Lizette
Garay-Rondero³

^{1,2} *National University of Science and Technology, International Maritime College, Sohar,
Oman,*

³ *Tecnologico de Monterrey, School of Engineering and Sciences, Institute for the Future of
Education, Nuevo León, Mexico*

*Corresponding author: Sb.issazadeh@gmail.com

Abstract

This research paper highlights the increasing number of maritime accidents and incidents in the European Union resulting from the constant cargo transportation by ships. The research study offers valuable insights and recommendations for enhancing maritime safety, catering to various audiences, including students, seafarers, managers, companies, shipbuilders, and researchers. The research aims to identify the causes of accidents in the maritime industry, both caused by humans and environmental factors. The goal is to analyze the data to understand these issues better and find ways to address them. The study highlights the importance of having unified standards and advanced solutions to improve maritime navigation and minimize accidents and environmental disasters. Collaboration among all stakeholders in the maritime industry is also essential to effectively address the challenges and risks associated with maritime transportation. Regular inspections and audits are also necessary to ensure compliance with regulations and standards. This research encourages everyone in the maritime industry to prioritize safety and take proactive measures to prevent accidents and incidents. The research paper explores the vital organizational, environmental, and human factors that impact personnel performance in the maritime industry. It stresses the connection between personnel, technology, and environmental conditions, underlining the importance of addressing human errors and enhancing personnel capabilities to reduce the likelihood of accidents and incidents in the maritime sector.

Keywords: Maritime Transport, European Maritime Safety Agency, National Transportation Safety Board, Human Factors.

1. Introduction

Analyzing European Union (EU) marine accidents, occurrences, and causes from 2014 to 2022 can help us understand policy and strategy reasons. Every recent year, the number of ships transporting cargo every 24 hours has skyrocketed, resulting in millions and billions of dollars and seafarer deaths each year. Many shipping companies and countries adopted it due to its low cost. With huge traffic everywhere, as the global population grows, many requirements, needs, and related products must be shipped from one place to another.

In addition, due to the maritime industry and technology, international trade has grown, requiring efficient and balanced management. Since they bear the load, sailors have a say, and their efforts are the triumphs of the marine industries and international trade.

Due to many accidents, general injuries, and marine pollution on the environment, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and other national and international administrative organizations were created to find the root causes and prevent them by establishing laws and regulations.

As a result, in this research, the authors will discuss the causes of these maritime catastrophes to infer that if they are not remedied, they may persist, endangering ships, sailors, their safety, and the marine environment. It may stop trade in an important site where numerous ships pass through on their way to their destinations.

Maritime safety decreases accident risks and pollutants by analyzing and studying fundamental causes, as mentioned and other sources do. The authors also found that, among other things, the problems are psychological and require further study, analysis, agreement, and monitoring for future success.

Because the annual losses in the maritime sector are not excessive, and the consequences of considering them and the status of the policy limit those losses, whether economic or human, resulting in the loss of many lives, reaching thousands annually, this requires reviewing them and arriving at a conclusion, such as taking more flexible and security measures for what is necessary while making sure to ensure their implementation.

Figures 1 and 2 show the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) 2014–2022 marine casualties and incidents by navigational region and ship type and the evolution of fatalities by a person on board (Nautilusint, 2024).

Figure 1. Marine casualties and incidents for the period (2014-2022), organized by navigational area and ship type, by EMSA (Nautilusint, 2024).

Figure 2. Evolution of fatalities, organized by category of the person on board (Nautilusint, 2024)

Furthermore, safety investigation reports showed a significant reduction from 2014 to 2022 compared to previous years (Nautilusint, 2024).

The target audience is researchers, academia, policymakers, and stakeholders. They can use the results of the analysis in training and future policies. They can also continue the investigation for more precise results and find details on maritime accidents and incident root causes.

On the other hand, this new study examines human and environmental factors in maritime transport accidents and disasters. It analyses charts, graphs, and data to determine the reasons for these incidents and disasters and emphasizes the need to improve safety to prevent economic, maritime, and environmental losses.

Overreliance on maritime transit and its expenses has escalated accidents. The article emphasizes maritime worker training that provides more flexibility, rest, and work time. This will boost international trade and improve navigational management. The report stresses the importance of following processes and investigations to improve maritime navigation.

The following sections are the following: The literature research provides information on vessels and damages from 10 significant EU incidents from 2014 to 2022. Briefings and conclusions from five authors' studies on these accidents follow.

The method Reviews reports and sources, analyses research methodology, and addresses human error-related mishaps. Global marine safety solutions are examined using graphs and graphics.

The Findings and Results section examines the causes of crew, ship, and cargo accidents. It discusses sailors' workload, inadequate education, constraints, and environmental, organizational, and technical issues that affect performance.

Also, in Discussions and Recommendations, Maritime accidents teach the significance of safety and standards to prevent human mistakes. They stress certifying sailors, prioritizing errors, and implementing level-appropriate approaches.

In conclusion, the study focuses on Human errors' effects on international maritime navigation, seafarers' lives, and the shipping business.

2. Literature Review

This section is divided into two subsections as follows:

2.1. Background

The authors have searched and seen a lot of the biggest binominal and accidents from 2014 to 2022 in the European Union because of the many accidents, marine environmental disasters, and others that changed the history of maritime navigation, which led long ago to the emergence of laws, systems, and regulations that serve for the safety and security of international shipping and improving matters related to global trade also by the International Maritime Organization and reducing those accidents. In the following table 1 are some accidents that happened in the European Union from 2014 to 2022:

Table. Ten accidents from 2014 to 2022 in the European Union (EMSA, 2023).

No	Vessel's Name	IMO Number	Location - Position	Year	The amount of damage
1	Nazmiye Ana	8516598	39°57.59' N - 0°1.41' E, SPAIN - Castellón	May 29, 2021	-Equipment Loss of ship - Constructive loss, two injured and 2 dead persons.
2	M/V Consouth & M/V Pirireis	9145255 & 7916727	36°10.07' N - 20°9.14' E, 78 nm WSW of Sapienza Islet at SW end of Peloponnese	April 29, 2013	-10 person death -limited oil pollution -Damages on accommodation, port aft quarter, forepeak tank, forecable deck, structural damages, and deformations at stem post.
3	Traditional vessel No 5 ELBE and container vessel Astrosprinter	NA - 9349215	053°37.6'N - 009°32.3'E, River Elbe off Stadersand	June 6, 2019	-Bow of each vessel -Astrosprinter: Paint abrasions on the starboard side of the bow; nobody was injured. - No 5 Elbe: Heavy damage to the underwater hull and foundered; eight people were injured, and minor pollution.
4	General cargo ship Daroja and the oil bunker barge Erin Wood	9148221 & Not IMO registered	57°26.36'N – 001°41.58'W, 4 nautical miles southeast of Peterhead, Scotland.	August 29, 2015	- ship Daroja: Indentation and scraping to bulbous bow. - Erin Wood: Shell plating fractures, flooding, superstructure damage, fuel cargo pollution.
5	Baltic Breeze & Mar De Marin	8312590 & 13584	42° 09,6' N - 008° 53,7' W, Estuary of the Vigo River (Pontevedra)	April 1, 2014	- BALTIC BREEZE: Cracks in the bulb and the port side hull liner deformation. - MAR DE MARIN: Gap on the starboard side of the hold. Total loss due to sinking - 5 dead & 5 injured due to bruises and symptoms of Hypothermia.
6	MT AL Oraiq & mv Flinterstar	9360790 & 9243758	N 62° 28.6' - E 006° 07.0', in the vicinity of the S3 buoy	October 6, 2015	-mts AL ORAIQ: Bulbous bow deformed and punctured. -mvFLINTERSTAR: Vessel lost – Oil spill.
7	M/V Transforza & Tugboat Kuguar	9199402 & 7020932	53°54,34' N - 014°15,70' E, the Bay of Pomerania – the Świna Strait	Feb 16, 2015	- Transforza: no damage. -Kuguar: The tugboat's hull plating was damaged on the port side below the waterline at a level of the engine room; the vessel was flooded with water and sank.
8	B/C Good faith	9076404	37° 58' 46'' N - 24° 43' 36'' E, NW Coast of Andros Island, Central Aegean Sea Greece	Feb 11, 2015	Sea and shore pollution from bunkers - Extended structural damages /semi-sinking/total loss.
9	RIG and Inger Marie	8801137 & NA	57°26,81' N – 011°27,17', Kattegat, Sweden	July 10, 2014,	- INGER MARIE foundered immediately after the collision, and the skipper perished. -RIG suffered minor damage to the port side anchor.
					-The hull of the fishing vessel: sustained

10	M/V As Rosalia & F/V Birincioğlu	9449845 & NA	NA, Northern Exit of the Istanbul Strait	June 17, 2021	partial damage, whereas the engine was destroyed. -The container vessel: sustained no damage.
----	----------------------------------	--------------	--	---------------	--

Here are the following explanations of each of those ten accidents:

2.1.1. Ship Nazmiye Ana

In 2021, the container ship NAZMIYE ANA was subjected to a capsizing in the port due to poor shipping due to a higher gravity at a particular center of the ship, and the approved stability book on loading conditions was not included in this distribution. Among them, what is lacking is that the captain and first officer have limited experience on this ship and that the ship itself was not included in specific programs to carry out the mission, stability accounts, or any other references that would help direct the ship's shipping operations regarding stability (CIAIM, 2021).

2.1.2. MV Consouth and MV Pirireis

In 2013, an accident occurred between two ships, M/V Consouth and M/V Pirireis, heading west of Sapienza Island at the southwestern end of the Peloponnese. On the south was first sighted after a few miles from the port bow side of the Pirireis ship, and the situation was safe for both ships until the Consouth ship collided with Pirireis towards her port aft quarter, which led to damage, entering the water and sinking. As for the other, it only suffered damage from the ship's bow and was floating, and the Pirireis ship sank with the shipment without any pollution in the sea at a depth of about 3000 meters (HBMCI, 2015).

2.1.3. Traditional Vessel No 5 Elbe and Container Vessel Astrosprinter

In 2019, the conventional ship had obstruction damage to the foremast sails, while the crew activists controlled it and failed to move to the correct lane side for its course. As a result, the vessel missed the oncoming routh and collided with the container ship Astrosprinter. With the support of the Deutsche Lebens-Rettungs-Gesellschaft (DLRG) (German Life Saving Association) and by chance being in the vicinity due to another mission, No. 5 ELBE was able to reach the mouth of the nearby Schwinge River on its own (BSU, 2021).

2.1.4. General Cargo Ship Daroja and the Oil Bunker Barge Erin Wood

In 2015, a collision occurred between the cargo ship Daroja and oil bunker barge Erin Wood, which resulted in contamination from leakage of the fuel cargo it was carrying and due to watchkeepers not keeping both ships unaware of the risk of collision. A lookout before that incident occurred. On the Daroja, the first officer missed opportunities to scout Erin Wood due to distraction and inattention.

On the other ship, the officer needed to be qualified despite the captain's presence and the vision of the ship Daroja, and the situation needed to be evaluated effectively. In the end, recommendations were made to both companies to improve navigation and control standards for maritime safety (MAIB, 2016).

2.1.5. Baltic Breeze and Mar De Marin

In 2014, while sailing through the southern channel to separate traffic from the mouth of the Vigo River, Pontevedra, the fishing vessel Baltic Breeze, and Mar De Marin collided. The collision led to the death of its crew after it sank in a few minutes, saving four others and one

person from outside the crew. The other ship suffered slight damage to the bow bulb. It was then provisionally classified as a severe accident.

The cause of the collision was human error by the second captain of the Mar De Marin ship. Due to the opposite direction of traffic, interference with the course of the Baltic Breeze ship, and an incorrect assessment of the situation, this error also prompted him to maneuver (CIAIM, 2016).

2.1.6. MT Al OraiQ and MV Flinterstar

In 2015, the bridge control team on board the ship mts AL ORAIQ did not perform the required tasks, and there was no comment on the decisions of the pilots also, on the VHF, they had a lack of awareness and did not question the overtaking of the mv Thorco Challenger on the right side and did not evaluate the distance to the buoy S3 Ship speed and expected traffic The situation near buoy S3, as the speed was maintained the same, which was not sufficient focus on the mv Flinterstar ship.

The two ships, MV Flinterstar and MT Al OraiQ collided near buoy S3. The parties agreed to prevent Flinterstar from sinking in the confined passage. Pilots on both ships believed MTS AL OriQ would push MV Flinterstar into a sandbank, which later happened (GNB, 2015).

2.1.7. MV Transforza and TugBoat Kuguar

In 2015, the deviation of the sailing ship to the port of Szczecin from the western side to the eastern side of the passage led to an error in the voyage plan, i.e., an incorrectly planned approach through the canal. It was found that Kuguar was sailing too close to the middle of the fairway and not as required under Regulation 9 part (a) of the Colreg 9 Convention, and the roads next to the tugboat sailing on the eastern side of the pass leading to Świnoujście.

Both ships had visual surveillance at the time, and they did not check their positions and the location of the other ships. The pilot of Transforza ignored the fact that there was no lookout man. In addition, he did not advise the master not to change the course after Passing Omskiy-137 by cutting the corner and going to the opposite side of the fairway (State Marine Accident Investigation Commission, 2016).

2.1.8. BC Good faith

In 2015, the bulk carrier Goodfaith was sailed at the ballast condition because of the prevailing bad weather conditions; when Goodfaith had almost cleared the strait in the night watch, the 2nd Officer took over the navigational watch while the Master left from the bridge at 0005, then at 0055 he called for the master that he reported the experiencing situation to Master, as Goodfaith had started to considerably drift to starboard notwithstanding her rudder was set hard to port and her engine to full ahead at 120 rpm,

Then, having assumed a steering failure, deployed the 2nd Officer, the Chief Engineer, and the able body seaman (AB) on the watch to the emergency steering gear operation. He did not observe any failure from steering, so the rudder was set hard to port. At 0100, Goodfaith was recorded at almost 1.7 nm off the NW Coast of Andros Island and heavily drifting to starboard. She was practically not under command, and her engine was running full ahead with 120 while making no headway.

After that, the imminent danger of an uncontrollable and violent grounding was ordered to alert the crew, and the general alarm was activated, facing the fact that the Goodfaith was not under command and was causing heavy rolling due to high waves and wind. Finally, the master reported dropping the anchors for the first officer and bosun to avoid the anticipated

grounding; nonetheless, it was impossible with the situation and weather conditions (HBMCI, 2017).

2.1.9. Rig & Inger Marie

In 2014, both vessels, the Rig and Inger Marie accident, which it has presented a possible explanation of what caused the collision; based on the detailed information, a conjunction of circumstances led to the collision that was overall caused by a lack of effective look-out on both ships, especially on Inger Marie vessel due of some work, once the Inger Marie was acknowledged on Rig, it was too late to avoid the collision, because on Rig they minimized the use of the radar, due to the excellent weather conditions that gave a good overview of the situation (DMAIB, 2015).

2.1.10. MV AS Rosalia and F/V Birincioğlu

In 2021, container vessel As Rosalia started departed from Haydarpaşa Port for Romania; she was not able to join the strait and stood by in drift for approximately 6.5 hours due to the traffic in the Istanbul Strait, then she started joining the strait accompanied by the pilot, While M/V As Rosalia was approaching the exit of the Strait to the Black Sea, she collided with fishing vessel Birincioğlu, So it found the M/V As Rosalia failed to change her course and speed on time and effectively to avoid.

The accident was caused by the fishing vessel passing through the traffic separation line, which obstructed the passage of the transiting vessel and made it feel close to the bow of the merchant vessel to avoid collisions (Transport Safety Investigation Center, 2021).

2.2. Background of Research

These things that the authors are making, also some people before they made, so the authors worked well before continuation of those things because the other had their job as what they discussed and directions of their research about maritime accidents for the specified period of them regarding their works, so the following examples are for people which the authors will be talking about their research works:

i. Ibn Awal and Hasegawa (2017) discussed the following in their research papers: "A Study on Accident Theories and Application to Maritime Accidents." They discuss maritime accidents with examples, such as the Titanic (1912) and Costa Concordia (2012), which are good examples in his work that prove some lessons to be addressed about the regulation and policy in the maritime industry.

Furthermore, this led to dealing with and analyzing these accidents as a problem and how to develop and use new technology to address a fundamental problem in safety science. authors also touched on the issue of the different types of accident theories and models, which have radical aspects, and the conclusions from them were related to safety in the various accident models discussed.

ii. Cao et al. (2023) are being made "research in marine accidents: A bibliometric analysis, systematic review, and future directions." Which talked about ideas for developing marine accident research, including future directions and implications. Accidents are selected and used from about 491 kinds of literature related and summarized in their research.

They divided the study into two sections: accident consequences and an analysis of the influential factors. I also took the Web of Science database from 2000 to 2022 to visualize information and some tools for scientific analysis using both CiteSpace and VOSviewer.

iii. Ki and Na (2017) researched "Development of a Human Factors Investigation and Analysis Model for Use in Maritime Accidents: A Case Study of Collision Accident

Investigation." It has been argued that about 80% or more of all maritime accidents are entirely or less caused by humans, so the International Maritime Organization introduced the Accident Investigation Act to prevent similar accidents and improve maritime safety.

The process consists of examining the proposed human factors. It provides a three-step organizational method: collect data and determine the sequence of occurrence; identify and classify essential human factors using marine and human factor analysis; and finally, develop safety procedures using causal chains. This method influences the development of safety procedures and identifies factors to provide safety and prevent accidents.

iv. Issa Zadeh et al. (2022) have been researching and discussing "Analysis of European Union Maritime Casualties Crisis Management Prospective." They spoke about maritime accidents and incidents in the European Union's fleets from 2011 to 2018 and analyzed figures and some numbers of accidents and incidents, such as sea pollution, people losing their lives, and injuries.

Comparing data and practical factors to reduce accidents and incidents due to their economic and marine environmental impacts, and how to control their consequences by lowering them by conducting some analyses and the root causes that led to these accidents.

v. Dominguez Péry et al. (2021) talked in their work about "Reducing maritime accidents in ships by tackling human error: a bibliometric review and research agenda." Therefore, in their scientific research, they discussed the leading cause of marine accidents resulting from direct and indirect error resulting from humans, especially with the increasing size of cargo ships, and what lies behind any accident among them that may cause spillage and marine pollution and have catastrophic consequences for the environment and the economy as well.

The added analysis of the top 20 authors cited both shipping accidents and human error. His study aimed to enhance the field of human error in the context of maritime transport, understand the role of human error, and ultimately benefit seafarers, students, and education as an addition to educational and academic curricula.

3. Methodology

This section is divided into four sections as follows.

3.1. Literature Review

The research uses a literature review, the internet, national and international unions, organizations, and internationally recognized reports to identify the root causes of marine accidents and human error factors. The authors add relevant reports from the EMSA website, expressing the causes, factors, and extent of losses. The cost and details are provided in the second chapter.

3.2. Database

The authors' review of annual reports on casualties in European Union waters from 2014 to 2022 found that human error played a more significant role in accidents than natural factors or external human error. The research collected data from 10 major accidents in the EU and compared them. The findings highlight the need for global solutions for sea safety, as annual casualties are high across various ship categories and not solely due to one factor.

3.3. Graphs and Pictures

The authors presented in this research paper some statistics and numbers in the form of graphs and pictures of the development of deaths, as well as m

marine casualties and incidents for the period (2014-2022), including a comparison between some of them from other years and statistics, according to the European Maritime Safety Agency.

4. Finding and Results

4.1. Contributing Factors of Accidents & Incidents

Accidents and incidents are often caused by one contributing factor or several factors, as shown in the following figure.3 shows the percentage of contribution between 2014 and 2022 to distinguish the contribution rate of each factor and type of accident event.

Figure 3. The percentage of contributing factors for 2014-2022 is organized by contributing factor types and accident event types (Nautilusint, 2024).

As you can see, human action is the primary type of accident event in Figure 3. Then, the rest of the contributing factors come behind it. Therefore, accidents are divided into shipboard operation, external environment, or shore management. Thus, the analysis in the previous form shows that the most critical factor is shipboard operation type, at 69.9% of all other contributing factors.

4.2. Marine Accidents and Incidents

Marine accidents can significantly impact individuals and the ship, including its equipment, payload, and environment. These incidents can be broadly classified into two main categories:

- Accidents that occur to the crew,
 - And accidents and incidents that affect the ship and its cargo.
 Furthermore, marine accidents and incidents are caused by reasons that are the most prominent examples of marine events. The following two figures show the analyses for the development of events on board the ship and the evolution of occurrences with persons and vessels for the period 2014 - 2022:

- Capsizing/Listing
- Collision
- Fire/explosion
- Flooding/foundering
- Damage to equipment
- Loss of control
- Hull fail
- Missing
- Contact

Figure 4. The evolution of occurrences with persons is organized by deviation source (EMSA, 2023).

Figure 4 shows the evolution of occurrences with persons, organized by deviation from 2014 to 2022, taken by EMCIP. It shows the failure rate, Body movement, Loss of control, etc.

Authors conclude from Figure 4 that there are causes and effects to all these numbers of occurrences with persons and can be from at least one of the following factors:

- Inadequate education/training.
- Inadequate equipment management.
- Inadequate manning.
- Workload.
- Inappropriate operation.
- Time pressure.
- Beak of safe manning level.

Figure 5. The evolution of occurrences with the ship is organized by casualty event type (EMSA, 2023).

Figure 5 shows the total number of occurrences with ships from 2014 to 2022, including the collision rate, loss of propulsion power, fire/explosion, etc.

4.3. Human Error and Organizational Factors

Issa Zadeh et al. (2022) as stated by identified in his conference research paper, there are organizational factors that affect the seafarers, which are caused by the following four preconditions:

- **Unsafe supervision:**

- 1- Inadequate supervision.
- 2- Planned inappropriate supervision.
- 3- Failed to correct problems.
- 4- Supervisory violations.

- **Precondition of unsafe acts:**

- 1- Substandard condition of operator.
- 2- Substandard practice of operation.

- **Unsafe act:**

- Errors

- 1- Skill-based errors.
- 2- Decision errors.
- 3- Perception errors.

- **Violations**

- 1- Routine violations.
- 2- Exceptional violations.

4.4. Effect of Technology on Personnel

Issa Zadeh et al. (2022) reported that simulators are increasingly used to assess and train employees. The use of genuine situations is costly, limiting, and harmful. Before hiring, personnel might be tested for alertness, memory, multitasking, and management. Continued training and drills can also keep people awake.

The author also noted that anthropometry, ergonomics, tool arrangement, technical, navigational, and operational equipment can affect people's performance. Data from manageable and critical equipment must be collected for easy user comprehension. Responsible people must maintain essential appliances and equipment, and senior authorized staff must make periodic checks. Figure 6 shows technology-personnel interaction.

Figure 6. Interaction between technology and personnel (Issa Zadeh, 2022).

4.5. Effect of Organizational Factors on Personnel Performances

Issa Zadeh et al. (2022) state that organizational aspects include all workplace norms and regulations. A company or technical manager can affect work scheduling and communication. Others, including safety culture and training programs, require practical and precise policies from industrial policymakers or company leaders. As mentioned, human error causes about 65% of accidents and incidents.

As indicated in Figure 7, environmental and organizational elements affect the organization-personnel relationship:

Figure 7. Interaction between organization and personnel (Issa Zadeh, 2022)

Organizational factors can be categorized as human factors as they are influenced by managers and policymakers who are human beings. Moreover, mistakes in equipment design and environmental factors can also be considered human factors, leading to environmental issues in the industry. For instance, system or equipment failure accounts for 20% of the issues, agents and other vessels contribute to 9% of the problems, and hazardous material is responsible for 3%.

4.6. Effect of Environmental Factors on Personnel Performances

Issa Zadeh et al. (2022) declared that environmental circumstances can impair maritime workers' decision-making, risk-taking, and weariness. Policymakers and employers must monitor rules, economic conditions, and employee lifestyle and nutrition to maximize performance. The economy and law can directly affect employee risk-taking.

As demonstrated in Figure 8, industrial or company managers cannot regulate noise, temperature, or sea state, but they can minimize their consequences.

Figure 8. Interaction between environment and personnel (Issa Zadeh, 2022).

4.7. The Maritime System is a People System.

According to Issa Zadeh et al (2022), it is vital to recognize that people interact with technology, the environment, and organizational elements. Performance depends on the relationship between these three components and their staff. Poor personnel communication can cause accidents, but the above linkages are even more vital in preventing them, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Maritime system (Issa Zadeh, 2022).

A marine operation's personnel include the ship's crew, pilot, port crew, traffic control staff, and administrative staff. As humans, these people have limitations and abilities that affect their performance. Poor performance may cause an accident.

Skills can be learned through training and education. Thus, an EMSA member state's maritime systems authorization department should prioritize this to improve marine crew performance. This can be done by improving training quality and quantity. This includes knowledge, management, and abilities. These abilities and limits are shown below:

- Knowledge
- Skill
- Multi-task performing

- Memory
- Motivation
- Alertness
- Management

5. Discussions and Recommendations

5.1. Ways to Reduce Maritime Accidents

This research paper shows that human errors cause more maritime disasters than other errors, with some discussions and analyses to show how important it is to create this maritime issue and find solutions that help the marine environment and industry prevent sea life pollution and other accidents. This chapter will address the most prevalent human errors, the following points, and the values learned from maritime accidents, which include numerous lessons to maintain maritime navigation safety (Krist, 2017):

A. Bridge Resource Management

When pilots are confronted with limited reaction times and close hazards, it becomes crucial to have all available resources at hand to ensure the safe operation of vessels. These resources include human resources and equipment, and their optimal utilization falls under the purview of Bridge Resource Management (Krist, 2017).

B. Proper Safety Equipment

Vessel owners, operators, and crew members are responsible for guaranteeing that the safety equipment on board is appropriately maintained and functioning. They should also ensure that the vessel is equipped with the necessary safety equipment to handle emergencies and offer the highest possible chance of survival for everyone on board (Krist, 2017).

C. Distractions

One of the highest priorities regarding safety improvements is minimizing distractions. Although operators must communicate with dispatchers and crew members and perform other work duties such as checking equipment and instruments, anything hindering proper vessel operation can result in tragic outcomes (Krist, 2017).

D. Fatigue

Fatigue is one of the foremost common reasons for transportation malfunctions, and reducing this could be the best need for the Security Board. The distribution emphasizes the reality that sailors ought to be mindful of how rest misfortune influences their execution and ought to abstain from tolerating an observation in a state of weakness that renders them unfit for obligation.

In such occurrences, sailors ought to prearrange for another qualified person, i.e., a watchstander, to serve in their put when conceivable. If is usually not conceivable, sailors ought to only accept obligation once they are satisfactorily rested and able to execute their commitments securely (Krist, 2017).

E. Investing in Infrastructure

Developing and maintaining robust maritime infrastructure, such as port facilities and emergency response systems, is critical to effectively preventing and containing accidents (Krist, 2017).

F. Prioritizing Training and Education

Emphasize the importance of comprehensive training programs that can empower maritime professionals and reduce the likelihood of accidents due to human error. By developing refresher courses and assessments for students, they can achieve qualifications that will enable them to practice their maritime profession effectively (KRIST, 2017).

G. Fostering Global Collaboration

Strengthening international cooperation by sharing information, conducting joint exercises, and coordinating emergency plans is essential. This will enhance the industry's safety measures and help prevent fraud that leads to accidents. This will also promote introducing operational methods and simulations to improve training and knowledge levels. It also includes enforcing strict safety guidelines to minimize ecological consequences (Krist, 2017).

H. Standard Maintenance and Repair Procedures

The National Transportation Safety Board is responsible for investigating accidents due to one or more individuals failing to comply with standardized procedures for inspecting, repairing, and maintaining equipment. Those who carry out these procedures must use accurate parts and tools and follow the exact specifications to ensure safe equipment operation and system integrity. They need to be trained as operators and familiar with the maintenance of equipment and appliances when the cases require it (Krist, 2017).

I. Inadequate Communication

Communication skills, whether limited or poor language on board ships, may affect the understanding of many things and may result in the need to develop them, including the salvation of communication and public exchange of experiences, consultation, and training with others. What contributes to its continuity is the linguistic development of the sailor, which facilitates and reduces communication risks at work (Krist, 2017).

J. Inadequate General Technical Knowledge

It is related to the training and professional education system and must be monitored and supervised by refreshment courses and evaluations (Issa Zadeh, 2022). So, it will have many benefits, helping the trainers or cadets develop themselves better for the future and paying more attention to the highest number of accident incidents, minimizing the rate of this issue and affecting the other generations of coming fresher seafarers for this career (Krist, 2017).

5.2. Discussion of Maritime Accidents

The authors emphasized that humans have a fingerprint of mistakes, requiring action to set limitations for every weakness on ships and qualify sailors to be sailors.

To fix them, classify human errors, prioritize them by severity, train sailor operators, and define shipboard operator standards. Sailors must examine ship reality to determine their strengths and weaknesses and improve to qualify for the position.

Educational institutions can recognize the graduation of large batches of sailors from different nationalities annually. The question arises regarding who is qualified and who can handle the operators on board ships and make decisions.

Therefore, it is recommended that measures and standards be taken to help sailors supervise this profession and reduce the possibility of danger by analyzing the severity of risks, their results, and their aspects.

5.3. Patterns of Accidents

In this subsection, the authors attempted to classify marine incidents according to their trajectories and severity, as presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Clustering results (Paolo & etc., 2020).

Clusters	Accidents Description
Cluster 1	This is the most numerous clusters. It mainly includes collision and grounding casualties involving cargo ships. While bad weather conditions are recognized as a common cause of these accidents, the human factor does not play an essential role in this group.
Cluster 2	Group's collision or grounding casualties in coastal waters. The lack of supervision and errors in management procedures (software factors) are reported among the leading causes of these accidents.
Cluster 3	This group of accidents concerns fire or machinery failures caused by technical problems. The human element does not play an essential role in this group of accidents.
Cluster 4	Group work accidents are associated with no specific causes.
Cluster 5	Incorrect operations cause group work accidents due to inadequate supervisory policy (software factors).
Cluster 6	It mainly groups accidents caused by a cargo-related problem. This type of accident frequently occurs in the open sea and causes the total loss of the ship. No specific causes linked to human factors emerge.
Cluster 7	Groups work accidents for which human errors (error in judgment and failure to respond appropriately) and/or human violations (routine violations) are reported as the main cause. In this type of accident, an inadequate standard of personal competence combined with hardware and software deficiencies induces the occurrence of human errors and violations.
Cluster 8	Groups work accidents during cargo operations. The main causes of these accidents are technical problems connected with human failures (error in judgement, incorrect operation of controls, failure to respond appropriately, routine and necessary violations). Even in this group, hardware and software deficiencies combined with communication problems and inadequate standards of personal competence play a key role in inducing human errors and violations.
Cluster 9	This includes work accidents and grounding casualties caused by a human failure induced by software deficiencies, lack of communication or coordination, inadequate standards of competence, or fatigue.

Cluster 10	This group's accidents are mainly grounding, or collision casualties caused by navigational tool problems and consequent inappropriate route choices. Communication problems related to fatigue and software deficiencies are recognized as contributing factors.
Cluster 11	The accidents in this group concern machine failures combined with technical problems. The latter are often caused by incorrect control operation and hardware deficiencies.

This research study presents cluster analysis approaches to divide the IMO database into groups of accidents that share similar characteristics. Cluster analysis is an unsupervised technique to identify relationships between observations in unlabeled data (Paolo & etc., 2020). Table 2 displays the clustering results of marine accident descriptions, specifically showcasing 11 distinct groups that reveal trends of accidents.

These human error clusters emerge from procedural and operational failings that serve the marine industry and its security, not work environment or equipment deficiencies. Since many countries depend on maritime transportation for their economies locally or externally, specialist training to improve safety protocols is developed.

This will cost them if future international marine navigation disasters occur. Human errors account for much of the time compared to other components, hence the writers' discussion of them. This indicates the need for more human supervision for ship work due to poor quality, possibly due to limited training for sailors.

This harms sailors due to work fatigue and lack of rest, which may lead to an accident. Human failure and its violations may also affect international shipping operations. However, it is possible to end this issue by implementing more stringent and unified procedures that serve the maritime sector.

6. Conclusion

This section comprises three primary components: the main objective, the outcomes, and the research limitations. Additionally, it concludes with potential directions for the continuation of this study.

6.1. Results

In conclusion, this research paper highlights the increasing number of maritime accidents and incidents in the European Union due to continuous cargo transportation. It emphasizes the need for policies and strategies to address the causes of these accidents, which result in significant economic losses and risks to seafarers. The study focuses on human and environmental causes of accidents,

We aim to categorize and analyze data to understand better and address these issues. It calls for unified standards and advanced solutions to enhance maritime navigation and reduce accidents and environmental disasters. Collaboration between stakeholders increases training and education for seafarers, and regular inspections and audits are also crucial. The research calls for all stakeholders to prioritize safety, take proactive steps to prevent accidents and protect the environment, seafarers, and the global economy.

This research paper explores the factors influencing personnel performance in the maritime industry, highlighting the interplay between personnel, technology, and environmental conditions. It emphasizes addressing human errors and enhancing personnel capabilities to mitigate accidents and incidents.

Organizational factors like inadequate education, equipment management, and supervision significantly impact personnel performance. Environmental conditions like noise, temperature, and sea state also impact personnel performance. The study highlights the need for specific training to improve safety procedures and the critical role of maritime shipping in supporting economies. It calls for a strategic effort to improve training, education, and management in the maritime industry to enhance safety measures, prevent accidents, and safeguard the marine environment.

6.2. Limitations

The authors faced many limitations with this research paper. They were not like the challenges he had to overcome due to circumstances outside his decisions, such as the lack of time due to the academic pressure around him, which resulted in dividing time and, from time to time, being late in completing some tasks. In addition, during this research paper, much research was required from international sources and other researchers to benefit from them.

Some of the information requested by the authors was unavailable, which took longer. One of the most prominent challenges during the research period or before starting was concern about the possibility of a lack of data that would serve the topic presented in this research paper, which would result in a lack of informational sources for discussion in the research paper.

Finally, working individually was a challenge for the authors, given that the work involved much effort, conclusions, developing diverse opinions, and much research for the required information, compared to if there was more than one member of the group, which would lead to the division of work and effort, which would give diverse opinions and creativity in the intellectual summary of this research paper.

6.3. Recommendation for the Future

The information in this study paper regarding maritime environmental mishaps and disasters will be helpful to future generations of academics and students. They can learn much and incorporate that knowledge into their upcoming papers and projects. In addition, seafarers and shipping firms must consider the significance of this matter and how it will affect them. They must work and abide by maritime law to prevent marine mishaps and fatalities.

Establish guidelines and rewards to support the maritime industry. We need to train sailors effectively to become competent in real-world situations. Technological advancements allow us to provide education with innovative and improved teaching methods. This can be improved by having a system to assess performance and levels for ongoing improvement and success monitoring.

References

- Nautilusint. (February 2024). European safety stays on course. Nautilus International. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/telegraph/european-safety-stays-on-course/>.
- Nautilusint. (February 2024). Marine casualties and incidents for 2014-2022, organized by navigational area and ship type. Image: EMSA. Nautilus International. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/telegraph/european-safety-stays-on-course/>.
- Nautilusint. (February 2024). The category of the person on board organises the evolution of fatalities. Image: EMSA. Nautilus International. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/telegraph/european-safety-stays-on-course/>.

- Nautilusint. (January 2020). Safety in numbers – the latest digest of European maritime casualty figures. Nautilus International. Available: <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/telegraph/safety-in-numbers-the-latest-digest-of-european-maritime-casualty-figures/>.
- Fan, S., Blanco-Davis, E., Yang, Z., Zhang, J., & Yan, X. (2020). Incorporation of human factors into maritime accident analysis using a data-driven bayesian network. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 203.
- Comisión de Investigación de Accidentes e Incidentes Marítimos de Spain (CIAIM). (2021). *Vuelco del buque de carga general NAZMIYE ANA en el puerto de Castellón, el 28 de mayo de 2021*.
- Hellenic Bureau for Marine Casualties Investigation (HBMCI). (2015). *Marine Casualty Safety Investigation Report 06/2013 Collision between M/V Consouth & M/V Pirireis 78 n.m WSW of Peloponnese-Greece Foundering of M/V Pirireis Loss of ten crew members of Pirireis*.
- Federal Bureau of Maritime Casualty Investigation (BSU). (2021). *Investigation Report 211/19 Very Serious Marine Casualty Collision between traditional vessel No 5 ELBE and container vessel ASTROSPRINTER on the River Elbe on 8 June 2019*.
- Marine Accident Investigation Branch (MAIB). (2016). *Report on the investigation of the collision between the general cargo ship Daroja and the oil bunker barge Erin Wood 4 nautical miles south-east of Peterhead, Scotland, on 29 August 2015*.
- Comisión de Investigación de Accidentes e Incidentes Marítimos (CIAIM). (2016). *Abordaje entre el buque mercante Baltic Breeze y el buque pesquero Mar De Marin en la ría de Vigo (Pontevedra), el 1 de abril de 2014, en el que fallecieron cinco tripulantes del pesquero*.
- Gemeenschappelijk Nautisch Beheer Scheldegebied (GNB). (2015). *Report on the joint investigation of the collision between the LNG Carrier mts AL ORAIQ and the mv FLINTERSTAR off the coast of Belgium on 6 October 2015 with the total loss of the mv Flinterstar*.
- State Marine Accident Investigation Commission. (2016). *Final Report 07/15 Very serious marine casualty M/V Transforza Tugboat Kuguar Collision of Transforza and Kuguar in the fairway in Świnoujście on 16 February 2015*.
- Hellenic Bureau for Marine Casualties Investigation (HBMCI). (2017). *Marine Casualty Investigation Report 07/2015 Grounding Of B/C Goodfaith Ov Andros Island Ov 11-02-2015*.
- Danish Maritime Accident Investigation Board (DMAIB). (2015). *Rmarine Accident Report March 2015, RIG and Inger Marie Collision on 10 July 2014*.
- Republic of Turkey Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure, Transport Safety Investigation Center. (2021). *Very Serious Marine Casualty Investigation Report*.
- Ibn Awal, Z. and Hasegawa, K. (2017). A study on accident theories and application to maritime accidents. *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 194, pp. 298-306.
- Cao, Y. et al. (2023). Research in marine accidents: A Bibliometric Analysis, systematic review, and Future Directions. *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 284.
- Tae Ki, H. and Na, S. (2017). Development of a human factor's investigation and analysis model for maritime accidents: A collision accident investigation case study. *Journal of Navigation and Port Research*, vol. 41(5), pp. 303-318.
- Issa Zadeh, B. (October 2022). Analysis of European Union Maritime Casualties Crisis Management Prospective. *Researchgate*. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369480519_Analysis_of_European_Union_Maritime_Casualties_Crisis_Management_Prospective.
- Dominguez-Péry, C., Narasimha Raju Vuddaraju, L., Corbett-Etchevers, I. and Tassabehji, R. (2021). Reducing maritime accidents in ships by tackling human error: A bibliometric review and research agenda - journal of shipping and trade. *Springer Link*, vol. 6.
- European Maritime Safety Agency. (October 2023). An annual overview of marine casualties and incidents 2023. EMSA. Available: <https://www.emsa.europa.eu/publications/item/5052-annual-overview-of-marine-casualties-and-incident.html>.

- Midas Global Maritime Pvt Ltd. (n.d.). Maritime accidents: What can we learn from them? *LinkedIn*. Retrieved May 04, 2024, from: https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/maritime-accidents-what-learn-from-them-vzjmc?trk=public_post.
- Krist, S. (September 2017). Ten ways to reduce the risk of maritime accidents. *The Maritime Executive: Maritime News*. [Online]. Available: <https://maritime-executive.com/editorials/ten-ways-to-reduce-the-risk-of-maritime-accidents>.
- Paolo, F. et al. (2021). Investigating the role of the human element in maritime accidents using semi-supervised hierarchical methods. *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol.52, pp.252-259.
- Paolo, F. et al. (2021). Investigating the role of the human element in maritime accidents using semi-supervised hierarchical methods. *Transportation Research Procedia*. [Table.2], vol.52, pp.252-259. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352146521000582?ref=pdf_download&fr=RR-2&rr=87f0c3d39fe0de57.